

Exotic Composite states in Nature

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Abstract

In this note essentially two exotic composite states are speculated using quark model. These particles as we suggest that they are real and are pentaquark states.

Last century physics have witnessed the discovery of several unknown particles in cosmic rays which was then further analyzed using high energy cyclotrons or particles accelerators. The first predicted meson was unveiled in 1947 by C.F. Powell and was first mistakenly identified as muon but later named as pion or pi meson. The proposal that what we called as elementary particles are actually not elementary but composed of tiny point like fundamental entities called quarks was revolutionary. A first quark of first generation was discovered in 1968 by SLAC. In this paper we will suggest two new states composed of four valence quarks and one antiquark. Recall that proton has charge of +1 in the units of e and neutron has no charge and both are fermions. In this note we will use quark notation as q and antiquark as q_0 . The particles which we find are as follows. First particle is of state given by udd_0du which bears a charge of +1 clearly equal as proton. "u" is the up quark and "d" is the down quark. Second state is quite similar but a slight change; the particle is composed of duu_0ud and has no charge or neutral. The suggested decays as follows

$$udd_0du \rightarrow p(\text{proton})$$

$$udd_0du \rightarrow e_0(\text{positron})$$

And various possible decays which need experiments to look for them.

For second state

$$duu_0ud \rightarrow n(\text{neutron})$$

We do not suggest that the predicted decays are obvious it might well be wrong and one needs experimental observation to confirm or disprove all ideas presented above.